

Interesting Findings Listed By Participants			unexpectedness	actionability
1802: earliest acquisition is a Singosari sculpture; the record shows that it has been returned		new findings, but not relevant	1	0
Combining Suriname expedition and looking at the them on the heatmap gives a very clean picture of how locations are connected, also globally		previously unknown geographical pattern	both	1
Geographical location is often recorded on a local level and it is difficult to find all objects from one country if one is unfamiliar with location name.		potentially interesting; not available now	-1	0
Maps gives you completely unusual insight in how many objects there are from one place. The timeline on the map is nice but the acquisition heatmap is useful.		new findings, surprised to see geographical trend	both	1
Nice to go from a heatmap to go from the heatmap to a historical event: Conflict by Fujita		new findings, useful	0	1
Futila conflict, I wasn't aware of multiple actors having multiple ownership (not looked into donation or purchase) to the museum		new findings, about provenance connection	both	1
Futila 2: I also found out that not all the objects were in the ___ collection first. That is my assumption but it is not the case.		contradiction with belief	both	1
From "Type" hoofdtoeien: come from Tapanahoni (river) in Suriname.			-1	1
All of these have as "transferred Title From" Ministerie van Kolonien.			-1	1
All of these have as collected in 1927		contradiction with belief: data quality	1	1
This was on an expedition named "Tapanahoni Exhibition".		potentially interesting	0	1
They are all noted as having a "provenance type": schenking or Verwering.			-2	1
Family ties of Gerrit Schouden to Johanna Houssen, Suriname's first Geol Pointee.		connection revealed through semantic exploration	both	1
Wereldmuseum has only three related objects as its not seen as the same as to its previous named institutions.		contradiction with belief: data quality	both	1
Statistics chart by Type shows high prevalence of ___ objects are related to spiritual powers.		new findings, through data summarisation	1	2
3 Connected Historical Events with my place of origin of interest			1	2
Actor metadata visualisation related objects (+ how actors described objects)		potentially interesting; not available now	0	0
Positive Remarks = visualise the collectors		new finding; already found something useful very relevant to their research, unsought for	both	2
31 objects from Nias (all areas), only 2 objects have acquisition dates			-1	1
identified a person who "collected" objects from Nias, ___ 19th Century military			1	2
historical events was connected to the objects "expedition" Nias			-1	2
mention of annual report would look into that correspondence		potentially interesting; not available now	0	2
bio of the stakeholder most helpful in narrowing down time-frame		new findings, trend identified through visual	both	1
was interested in KNAG, found maatschappij connected to it that had interesting actor.			1	2
combination of institute and people helps filter and refine my research			0	2
focused on one actor who donated several hundreds of objects to the museums from one expectation.			1	2
actor-acquisition timeseries showed transfer date to museum in the 1920's but also in 2011		new finding; already found something useful very relevant to their research, unsought for	2	2

actor-acquisition gave the insight into ways actors have engaged with the museum over time (or might be a dating mistake)		new findings, trend identified through visual	both	1	1
RV-11671-10 from Breda; I would like to see album here -- did see it through the donar; looks like soldiers album		potentially interesting; not available now		1	-1
Lombok expedition historical event is interesting to have				-1	1
TM-82-1 Lombok painting, you can really see the Kris (dagger) in the painting; useful to see what a Lombok painting looks like		potentially useful		0	0
Georg Tillmann had several links to other people inc,		new finding; already found something useful	both	2	1
Found using actor search two variants of one name (Tillmann)		very relevant to their research, unsought for		-1	1
Wolf Tillman (a) name spelled wrong (lots of variants) (b) His father was Goerg				-1	1
Also connected to Beilina Indonesia Expedition and interesting an indonesia object from a ... expedition (TM-1772-1184)		new finding; already found something useful	both	2	2
			Average	0.4	1.142857143
			Standard deviation	1.062737863	0.7333587976